

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE 'OPEN DATA' CONCEPT IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

Bardadym Oleh Valeriiovych

ORCID 0000-0002-2777-6568

Master's degree candidate at the Department of Educational and Socio-Cultural Management and Social Work

Bohdan Khmelnytsky Cherkasy National University

bardadym.oleh520@vu.cdu.edu.ua

Supervisor: Shpylova Vera Oleksiivna

Modern digital technologies are transforming various social processes [1]. With the development of digital infrastructure[2], a new (networked) environment for the exchange of free data, knowledge and information between users has been formed. Let's take a closer look at the terms 'open data', 'open knowledge', 'open information' (see Table 1)

Table 1

Comparison of definitions of «open data», «open knowledge», «open information»

№	Terms	Author	Author's interpretation
1	Open data	“Open data is data that can be freely used, re-used and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike» <i>Source: https://opendatahandbook.org/guide/en/what-is-open-data/</i>	This data is free for use and can be distributed for any purpose. Example. Summer temperature 21, 25, 28, 18, 25, 27 degrees Celsius
2	Open information	«Open Information means government-owned information whose release is not subject to privacy, security or legislative restrictions and which is made available to the public with minimal restrictions on its use or re-use. This includes, but is not limited to, reports, studies, maps, legislation, etc. Open	This is open data that is combined or integrated into a context. Example. Average summer temperature 25.5 degrees Celsius

		information is released proactively whenever possible» Source: https://www.lawinsider.com/dictionary/open-information	
3	Open knowledge	«Open knowledge is what open data becomes when it's useful, usable and used» Source: https://okfn.org/en/library/what-is-open/	This is open data that is meaningful and verified and can be reused. Example. After rain in summer, temperatures drop by 5 degrees Celsius

At the heart of these three concepts, the main concept is 'open data'. Open data ensures: democratisation of information through free access to data for users; public control - increasing the transparency of organisations and ensuring monitoring of social processes; innovation - development of new knowledge and business models that promote equality. Open data can be classified according to the following criteria:

1. by format: text, structured, graphic, video, audio, geospatial, archival.
2. Access: closed, open Closed data is considered to be data that has restrictions on its use under the relevant licence.

The principles of open data are regulated by the Open Data Charter[3], which is based on the following principles: typical openness, efficiency and clarity, accessibility, structured and standardised, comparability and interoperability, community involvement, and inclusiveness.

Let's take a closer look at the characteristics of open data (see Table 2)

Table 2

Characteristics of open data

№	The sign	Description
1	Philosophy	Liberalism, network society
2	Technology	Internet, cloud computing, data centres
3	Usage	Commercial and non-commercial
4	Data editing	Mostly free use
5	Licence	You can modify them and use them in your commercial activities
6	Accessibility	Open for use
7	Values	Interaction between government, business and society, solving problems, improving services, improving understanding, creating a new business model

8	Legal restrictions	Use of non-personal data
9	Quality	Certified, relevant, accurate, interoperable
10	Standard	Data format and structure.
11	Information about the publication	Contains metadata (Source, funding, licence, publication history, author)

Open data is used in various fields. Public sector: Openbudget (<https://openbudget.gov.ua/>), public procurement Prozorro (<https://prozorro.gov.ua/uk>); budget monitoring E-Data (<https://edata.gov.ua/>); e-declarations of the NACP (<https://public.nazk.gov.ua/>); justice - electronic state registers (<https://opendatabot.ua/registry>); transport - traffic schedule (<https://www.eway.in.ua/ua/cities/kyiv>); environment - State Agency of Water Resources of Ukraine (<https://davr.gov.ua/>); healthcare E-health (<https://ehealth.gov.ua/>). There is also open data for the education sector.

In the course of the study, the following groups of open data were grouped and identified by the author for the education sector.

1. Open statistical datasets are public data of educational institutions (higher education, vocational higher education, vocational and technical, general secondary) on the number of students, number of teachers, number of persons enrolled in education, number of graduates, distribution of the population by level of education, licensed and unlicensed specialities, number of educational institutions, number of applications, rating lists, competitive proposals, salaries of teaching and research staff, distribution of the population by level of education and specialities.

Resources providing access to the statistical dataset: The Unified State Electronic Database on Education (<https://info.edbo.gov.ua/>), the State Statistics Service (<https://stat.gov.ua/>), the Institute of Educational Analytics (<https://iea.gov.ua/diyalnist/naukovo-analitichna-diyalnist/analitika/>).

2. Open monitoring data on the quality of education are public datasets that reflect the learning outcomes of pupils and students of educational institutions.

Resources that provide access to data sets related to monitoring the quality of education: Ukrainian Centre for Educational Quality Assessment (<https://testportal.gov.ua/stat/>), Pisa (<https://www.oecd.org/en/about/programmes/pisa.html>).

3. Open registers of educational documents is an open database containing information on: educational documents (higher education, vocational higher education, vocational and general secondary education), certificates of professional development of teachers, registers of external independent evaluation and national multi-subject test, student cards, certificates of student learning, certificates of educational sequence.

Resources that provide access to the statistical dataset The unified state electronic database on education (<https://info.edbo.gov.ua/>).

4. Open science data is public data created and collected in the scientific field. This type of data includes: scientific publications (articles, proposals, abstracts); datasets (statistical information, images, videos, tables); information about scientists (profiles, results of entrance and final exams, minutes of academic councils).

Implementation: creation of repositories such as Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>), public profiles of Orcid (<https://orcid.org/>), and Statista datasets (<https://www.statista.com/>).

Since open access has become available, it is equally important that scientific results are critically evaluated by other scientists so that open scientific data can be improved and verified for reliability;

5. Open Educational Resources (OER) are public ‘teaching and research materials that are created for sharing and for the purpose of disseminating pedagogical experience[4]. Teaching materials (lectures, textbooks, video lectures).

Implementation: open repositories (<https://naurok.com.ua/>).

6. Financial data public data on the financial activities of an educational institution. The availability of this data ensures: transparency of finances to the community; accountability - public responsibility for decisions made to the community; and cost estimation.

Implementation: creation of interactive datasets in the form of dashboards on: budget, revenues, expenditures, investments, procurement

7. Infrastructure data is public data on the infrastructure of a higher education institution. This may include information on the equipment of classrooms, laboratories and library stock.

Implementation: publishing information about classrooms, laboratories and library collections.

Thus, open data ensure effective management of an educational institution at various stages: strategic: studying and analysing labour market trends; identifying effective areas; financial: monitoring income and expenses; optimising costs; attracting investment; human resources management: analysing data on increasing staff productivity; studying factors that encourage employees to increase their motivation; infrastructure management: maximising the use of classrooms in an institution; monitoring the state of infrastructure; modernising premises; managing.

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3. Міжнародна хартія відкритих даних URL:

https://dostup.org.ua/request/47481/response/111982/attach/4/opendatacharter%20UKR.pdf?cookie_passthrough=1

4. Open Educational Resources (OER) URL: <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-educational-resources>